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ACHIEVING EDUCATIONAL SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOAL THROUGH CONFLICT MANAGEMENT IN NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY SYSTEM

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Abstract

The responsibility of societal care and ridding off hurdles of sustainable socioeconomic development lies on the sleeves of the higher educational institutions. The Universities become role models the public is looking forward to as enlightened segments of society for assistance. Invariably, the function of academic circles is very important to the accomplishment of any arrangement or policy for sustainably developed society.

Therefore, to manage the conflict in the university system, there is need to develop a constructive communication process that influences conflict negotiator's personality, utilizing appropriate leadership style of the school administrator, communication in University conflict management should be timely and sincerely, while the University authorities approach university affairs democratically or dialogical. Universities should develop curriculum for courses relating to conflict management and resolution, while the University management and the nation's leaders should create a non-violent strategic approach for discussion in managing conflicts on tertiary institutions issue in the country.

Key words: Educational Sustainable Development Goal, Sustainable Development Conflict, Conflict Management, Nigerian University System

Introduction

Various scholars have strongly believed a glaring relationship between education and development. Invariably, there should be no contention that education is the surest way to sustainably develop any people or society (Itari & Ugbe 2018). Education still remains the process of imparting and acquiring knowledge, skills, attitudes, values and experiences in institutions of learning, while living, at work or play. The acquired skills are subsequently applied to sustain present and future generation in everyday life. It is the proper nurturing, transmission and application of such skills and knowledge that guarantees development and sustenance of the society (Abiodun 2002). The responsibility of taking care of the society and getting rid of the hurdles in the way of sustainable socioeconomic development lies on the sleeves of the higher educational institutions.

The function of the higher educational institutions is to prepare the future managers, doctors, engineers, and social scientists to serve the people at larger level. The Universities (especially) become the role models and the public is largely looking forward to these enlightened segments of society to overcome the issues. It is obvious that the function of academic circles is very important to the accomplishment of any arrangement or policy for sustainably developed society (Altbach 2008). At the same time, it is widely recognized that there are barriers in the communication between academia and society. Over and over again, Universities in Nigeria have been in conflict within the societies over their missions and responsibilities, trying to meet the economic challenges and capacity building measures are on the way to make the education more viable to the community on the whole. The study seeks to proffer curative actions to achieve the desired sustainable development goal of education through efficient management of conflict in Nigerian University education system.

Sustainable Development

The adoption of the concept Sustainable Development (SD), as highlighted in the Brunt land Report and at the Stockholm Conference of 1972 (UNECA, 2012), was borne out of the global link between environmental problems and socio-economic concerns, also because earlier conceptions and approaches to development appeared to focus largely on economic and physical wealth despite the multi-dimensional and complex nature of development (Bellu, 2011).

Sustainable development connotes the creation and sustenance of the conditions for current and future generations of human to live well on this planet. Hence, as noted by Sims & Falkenberg, (2013) right from the beginning a multi-prong approach to the idea of sustainable society was taken that went beyond concerns for only the destruction of the national environment to include the concern for meeting the essential needs of all people and those needs are met in a sustainable way in consideration of the needs of future generations.

The Bruntland Report defined sustainable Development as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generation to meet their own needs”. Ahenkan and Osei-Kojo (2014) quoting the organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2001) also defines sustainable development as the development path along which maximization of human well-being for today’s generation, putting in mind the well-being of the future generation. This suggests that sustainable development considers the needs of the future and current generations in tandem, rooted in the pursuit of the well-being and welfare of the people. The objectives of sustainable development require the protection of the natural resources upon which future development depends.

- Sustainable development connotes equitable and balanced development among the citizenry (Suobbotina, 2004).
- Valuing nature and human life in an intrinsic way is an integral part of development (Bakar, 2005).
- Sustainable development will meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Ilechukwu et al 2014),

Sustainable Development Goal Four (SDG4)

Sustainable Development Goal Four (SDG4) gears towards all-inclusive and equitable quality education and promotion of lifelong learning opportunities for all. The emphasis under this goal has worldwide coverage of quality education from pre-school through at least secondary education, and then on to more advanced, skills training (Sachs, 2015). The goal is to build a nation that will facilitate a realization of the full potential of each child to contribute to building a just, tolerant and egalitarian society. The vision of an inclusive quality education reflects on the idea of education for all, principally for those groups who are seen to be vulnerable, with particular emphasis is on equal access to all and lifelong education.

In the Incheon Declaration and Framework for Action, approved in May 2015 at the World Education Forum in Incheon, Republic of Korea, made the following statement: The renewed education agenda captured in Goal 4 is comprehensive, holistic, ambitious, aspirational and universal, and inspired by a vision of education that transforms the lives of persons, communities and societies, leaving no one behind. The Declaration also outlines numerous critical processes to forestall impediment against the achievement of SDG 4, to include subjects of access, equity and inclusion with specific attention to gender equality, quality education and lifelong learning. Education, predominantly the all-inclusive and quality education is the focus of SDG 4, and is critical to all of the other SDGs and sustainable development in general (Buckler & Creech, 2014). SDG 4 is therefore a wise decision because education is the bedrock of any society that is willing to open up employment opportunities for all which help in bringing out individual from the shackle of unemployment and poverty; reduces societal inequalities and provide the knowledge and skills needed to live supportive lifestyles.

Objectives of Sustainable Development Goal Four (SDG4)

The International Education Framework and the 2030 Agenda, as cited by (Global Campaign for

Education, 2019) SDG4 is the education goal objectively based on guaranteeing all-inclusive and equitable education that promote lifelong opportunities for all. SDG4 is embodied with 10 definite targets/objectives which include:

1. By 2030, to ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes. The provision of 12 years of free, publicly-funded, inclusive, equitable, quality primary and secondary education of which at least nine years are compulsory, leading to relevant learning outcomes should be ensured for all, without discrimination.
2. By 2030, to ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care and pre-primary education so that they are ready for primary education. The provision of at least one year of

free and compulsory quality pre-primary education is encouraged, to be delivered by well-trained educators, as well as that of early childhood development and care.

3. By 2030, to ensure equal access for all women and men to affordable and quality technical, vocational and tertiary education, including university. It is imperative to reduce barriers to skills development and technical and vocational education and training (TVET), starting from the secondary level, as well as to tertiary education, including university, and to provide lifelong learning opportunities for youth and adults. The provision of tertiary education should be made progressively free, in line with existing international agreements.
4. By 2030, to substantially increase the number of youth and adults who have relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship. Equitable access to TVET needs to be expanded while quality is ensured. Learning opportunities should be increased and diversified, using a wide range of education and training modalities, so that all youth and adults, especially girls and women, can acquire relevant knowledge, skills and competencies for decent work and life. Beyond work-specific skills, emphasis must be placed on developing high-level cognitive and non-cognitive/transferable skills, such as problem solving, critical thinking, creativity, teamwork, communication skills and conflict resolution, which can be used across a range of occupational fields.
5. By 2030, to eliminate gender disparities in education and ensure equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for the vulnerable, including persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples and children in vulnerable situations. Emphasizing on inclusion and equity, all people, irrespective of sex, age, race, colour, ethnicity, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property or birth, as well as persons with disabilities, migrants, indigenous peoples, and children and youth, especially those in vulnerable situations or other status, should have access to inclusive, equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities. Vulnerable groups that require particular attention and targeted strategies include persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples, ethnic minorities and the poor. All girls and boys, women and men, should have equal opportunity to enjoy education of high quality, achieve at equal levels and enjoy equal benefits from education. Adolescent girls and young women, who may be subject to gender-based violence, child marriage, early pregnancy and a heavy load of household chores, as well as those living in poor and remote rural areas, require special attention. In contexts in which boys are disadvantaged, targeted action should be taken for them. Policies aimed at overcoming gender inequality are more effective when they are part of an overall package that also promotes health, justice, good governance and freedom from child labor.
6. By 2030, to ensure that all youth and a substantial proportion of adults, both men and women, achieve literacy and numeracy. The principles, strategies and actions for this target are underpinned by the contemporary understanding of literacy as a continuum of proficiency levels in a given context. It goes beyond the understanding of a simple dichotomy of 'literate' versus 'illiterate'. Therefore, action for this target aims at ensuring that by 2030, all young people and adults across the world should have achieved relevant and recognized proficiency levels in functional literacy and numeracy skills that are equivalent to levels achieved at successful completion of basic education.
7. By 2030, to ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including, among others, through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and nonviolence, global citizenship and appreciation of cultural diversity and of culture's contribution to sustainable development. It is vital to give a central place to strengthening education's contribution to the fulfillment

of human rights, peace and responsible citizenship from local to global levels, gender equality, sustainable development and health. The content of such education must be relevant, with a focus on both cognitive and non-cognitive aspects of learning. The knowledge, skills, values and attitudes required by citizens to lead productive lives, make informed decisions and assume active roles locally and globally in facing and resolving global challenges can be acquired through SDG4.

8. By 2020 to build and upgrade education facilities that are child, disability and gender sensitive and provide safe, non-violent, inclusive and effective learning environments for all. This target addresses the need for adequate physical infrastructure and safe, inclusive environments that nurture learning for all, regardless of background or disability status.
9. By 2020, to substantially expand globally the number of scholarships available to developing countries, in particular least developed countries, small island developing States and African countries, for enrolment in higher education, including vocational training and information and communications technology, technical, engineering and scientific programmes, in developed countries and other developing countries. Scholarship programmes can play a vital role in providing opportunities for young people and adults who would otherwise not be able to afford to continue their education. Where developed countries offer scholarships to students from developing countries, these should be structured to build the capability of the developing country. While the importance of scholarships is recognized, donor countries are encouraged to increase other forms of support to education. In line with the SDG 4 education by 2030 is focused on equity, inclusion and quality hence, scholarships should be transparently targeted at young people from disadvantaged backgrounds.
10. By 2030, to substantially increase the supply of qualified teachers, including through international cooperation for teacher training in developing countries, especially least developed countries and Small Island developing States. Teachers are the key to achieving all of the SDG 4 targets. It requires urgent attention, with a more immediate deadline, because the equity gap in education is exacerbated by the shortage and uneven distribution of professionally trained teachers, especially in disadvantaged areas. As teachers are a fundamental condition for guaranteeing quality education, teachers and educators should be empowered, adequately recruited and remunerated, motivated, professionally qualified, and supported within well-resourced, efficient and effectively governed systems.

Education for Sustainable Development

The truism that education is the surest way to sustainably develop any people or society needs no contention. Ilechukwu, et al, (2014) affirmed that in December 2002, the UN General Assembly adopted resolution 57/254 to put in place a United Nations Decade of Education for sustainable Development, spanning the years 2005 to 2014, with the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) as the lead agency for the Decade. The overall goal of the Decade for sustainable Development as reported by Ilechukwu et al (2014) is the integration of the principles, value and practice of sustainable development into all aspects of education and learning – social, informal, non-formal and formal. The decade's four key objectives according to authors are:

1. Facilitating, networking and collaborating among stakeholders in education for Sustainable Development (ESD)
2. Fostering greater quality of teaching and learning in ESD

3. Supporting countries in achieving their sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through education for sustainable development.
4. Provide countries with new opportunities and tools to incorporate ESD in education reforms efforts.

The political Development adopted at the World Summit on Sustainable Development (WSSD

2002) as quoted by Ilechukwu et al (2014), states that sustainable development is built on interdependent and mutually reinforcing pillars of economic growth, social/human development and environmental protection and sustainability. Education for Sustainable Development is therefore an approach to teaching and learning based on the ideals and principles that underlie sustainability. The role of education for sustainable development is to help people develop the attitudes, values, skills and knowledge to make informed decisions for the benefits of themselves and others, now and for the future, and to act upon those decisions. Chapter 36 of Agenda 21, adopted at the 1992 Earth Summit in Rio, identifies four major thrust of Education for Sustainable Development (Ilechukwu et al, 2014). They include:

- a. Promoting and improvement of basic education: It recognizes sustainable development requirement for changes in attitudes and values towards sustainability and development and that basic education has central role to play in achieving those changes. The necessity of basic education is to transform and improve the conditions of both the learner and the community towards (Association of African Universities, 2009).
- b. Reorienting existing education at all levels to address sustainable development. This involves educational reforms of principle, skills, perspectives and values that are qualitative, quantitative, appropriate and relevant to the socio-cultural and school curricula. It looks into the contents of what is being taught, the method and the education and professional development of those who are responsible for implementing education for sustainable development (Ilechukwu et al 2014).
- c. Develop public understanding and Awareness of sustainability: This requires a population that is aware of the goals of sustainable society with conscious efforts towards friendly environmental practices in tandem with improved health and sanitation (Ilechukwu et al 2014).
- d. Training: Training presupposes societal need for a literate and environmentally aware citizenry and workforce to help guide nations in the implementation of sustainable development goals. The need for all sections of the society to train their leaders and workers in environmental management, as training is distinct from education but specific to particular job or class of job (Ilechukwu et al, 2014).

University Educational System in Nigeria

Education is widely accepted as a major instrument for promoting socioeconomic, political and cultural development in Nigeria. Universities educate future leaders and develop the high-level technical capacities that underpin economic growth and development (Odekunle, 2001). Besides, the main purpose and relevance of university education in Nigeria is the provision of much needed manpower to accelerate the socio-economic development of the nation. Such specialized education at the higher level is regarded as an instrument of social change and economic development (Ibukun 1997) The role education generally and more especially higher education plays in facilitating the growth and development of a country's economy is significant (Ajayi &

Ekundayo. 2008). The National Policy on Education (2014) highlighted the goal of university education as follows:

- To contribute to national development through high level relevant manpower training.
- To develop and inculcate proper values for the survival of the individual and society.
- To develop the intellectual capability of an individual to understand and appreciate the local and external environment.
- To acquire both physical and intellectual skills which will enables individuals to be self reliable and useful member of the society.
- To promote and encourage scholarship and community service.
- To forge and cement national unity.
- To promote national and international understanding and interaction (FRN, 2014 p.2).

Universities in the Centre of Educational Sustainable Development Goal

It is imperative to understand that selecting university as a suitable leader for sustainable development cannot promise the triumph of the project exclusively. But the crucial issue is having a strong coordinator within university for sustainable development affairs to direct the researches and execution activities of the other stakeholders (Altbach, 2008). With the intention of achieving such status, the need for having a strong coordinator and secretariat in each university to hold, systematize and harmonize sustainable development related issues seems imperative due to the challenges and conflicts in various universities.

Challenges Confronting Nigerian Universities

Education in Nigerian Universities' education is confronted with several challenges. In the light of the sustainable development goal on education, this article seeks to highlight these challenges within the context of lack of a sound strategic plan, poor leadership, ineffective teaching and learning, poor researching activities, problems of inadequate infrastructure facilities, inadequate funding, poor international outlook (staff, students, research), the poor reputation of Nigerian Universities, academic corruption and fraud, low international ranking, lack of modern laboratories (Ajayi & Ekundayo 2009)..

1. Lack of Sound Strategic Plan:

Lack of a sound strategic plan constitutes one of the major challenges confronting the Nigerian Universities. Many Nigerian Universities lack plans that cover the unit level, the department level, and other sectors of the institution. No driving mission, vision, and goals at the various units of the Nigerian Universities. Some Universities are uncoordinated and unorganized for no strategic plan guiding their activities. In addition, no strategic plans for curriculum development, student's enrolment projection, manpower planning and development, Universities infrastructural facilities, Universities finance management, thus the academic programs of the Universities are not properly planned (Ojo 2018). Ogunode (2014) confirmed a poor implementation of academic programs in the Universities due to a lack of effective plans.and further stressed that many Nigerian Universities administrators do not work with the strategic plans of the Universities.

- Poor Leadership:

Another problem facing the Nigerian Universities is the poor leadership style of Vice-Chancellor. Many Nigerian University leaders emerged without due process, they are appointed by politicians with less qualification to handle academic institutions like the universities set up. They lack competence, leadership skills, and managerial skills to transform the Universities for sustainability. Creating setbacks to university system and causing problems that affect system performance include inadequate funding, inadequate coordination of curriculum, leadership problems, lack of infrastructural facilities, due to dictatorial, corrupt and non-flexible attitude in school governance (Udida, Bassey, Udofia, Ekaette, 2009).

- Ineffective Teaching / Learning Activities:

Ogunode (2018) observes that the quality of teaching and learning in Nigerian universities is poor and cannot guarantee the effectiveness of teaching. Eneh Ngozi, (2009) also submitted that student enrolment grows with the national population; more staff are not recruited to match the rate of growth of the student enrolment. This leads to an unmanageable student-teacher ratio. Consequently, the quality of education or learning and teaching dwindles because the increase in student enrolment does not receive a corresponding increase in material and staff inputs, but rather battles with decaying infrastructure and dwindling inputs.

- Poor Research Activities:

One of the functions of the Universities is to engage in research programs and solves the social, economic, and political challenges affecting the Nation through the findings. Due to the poor research programs and lack of research capital, many young researchers are discouraged to embark on researches. The Nigerian Universities' research income per academic and research staff, research income per institutional income, papers per research income is one of the poorest in the world. There has been poor research activities in Nigerian Universities, Okoli, Ogbondah, and Ewor, (2016) affirmed the poor attitude of governments towards research and inadequate funding of research programs.

- Inadequate Infrastructure Facilities:

Ojo (2018) observed that the problems of inadequate infrastructural facilities are another major constrain to the Universities education development in Nigeria. John, (2016) remarked that infrastructure facilities and laboratory equipment in our universities are not in good condition and majorities have even outdated. All the required resources for the education production process are in short supply that poses a hindrance to learning and research work. The dearth of infrastructure in the universities is sickening and runs short of an ideal academic environment.

- Inadequate Funding:

Inadequate funding is another major problem frustrating the development of Nigerian Universities.

Osunyanmi, Adebukola Foluke (2018) observed that the national budget in 2017 allocated N455.4 billion to education out of a total expenditure of N7.4 trillion; that is 6.1 percent. The 2018 budget proposal allocated

N605.79 billion to education out of a total expenditure of N8.6 trillion; that is 7.04 percent. Nigerian government is proposing to give the sector its lowest allocation in 10 years; 5.6 per cent, the lowest percentage allocation since 2011. A sum of N742.5 billion was allotted to education out of N13.08 trillion budgeted for next year, in the breakdown, N579.7 billion is for personnel cost, N35.4 billion for overhead cost, while N127.3 billion is dedicated to capital expenditure. The headquarters of the federal ministry of education was allotted N65.3 billion and the [Universal Basic Education](#), which supervises education at the primary and secondary levels got N77.6 billion. The remaining was shared across other institutions under the ministry (Premium Times, 2000).

- Poor International Outlook:

Another challenge confronting the Nigeria Universities is that of poor international outlook. The proportions of international staff and students in Nigerian Universities are low, and many Nigerian Universities lecturers are not in international collaboration with other universities for the purpose of sharing ideas and transferring knowledge. Insecurity and poor working environment have forced foreign lecturers back to their countries ((Hill, Beisiegel and Robin 2013). Also the proportion of Nigerian universities' total research journal publications co-authored by foreign lecturers is low compared to other African countries. Internationalization of a university shows the degree of its involvement in the global educational and scientific process.

- Poor Reputation of Nigerian Universities:

Majority of Nigerian universities are not well known in other parts of the globe for their low involvement in international collaboration and international research. The reputation of Nigerian Universities outside the geographical region of Africa is low. In recent times scholars and foreign students from other continents hardly visit Nigerian universities for exchange programs. Adeniyi (2012) argued that the National Universities Commission saddled with the responsibilities of managing universities in Nigeria is not doing well in rebranding and repackaging of the Nigerian universities in abroad.

- Academic Corruption and Fraud:

Transparency International places Nigeria at 136th place among 176 countries. Nigeria's education sector is particularly vulnerable to corruption. In 2013, Transparency International reported that about 30 percent of Nigerians surveyed said they had paid a bribe in the education sector. Recent reports that the documentary recorded the conversation (video and audio) showed how sex-trade for admission is rampant. The National Youth Service Corps has revealed that some tertiary institutions in Nigeria still sell degree, HND certificates to unqualified persons. According to Ararat Osipian (2013), academic corruption is linked to limited access to education³ has no doubt contributed to the use of bribes and personal connections to gain coveted positions in universities. Those who have no ability or willingness to resort to corruption face lost opportunities and unemployment (WENR, 2017)

1. Poor International Ranking:

Another problem confronting the Nigerian universities education is the problem of low ranking in the World Ranking Universities. The 2019 edition of Times Higher World University Rankings indicated that the three Universities in Nigeria – Covenant University, University of Ibadan, and the University of Nigeria, Nsukka – have been included in the 2019 Times Higher Education World University Rankings. The list, launched on Wednesday at Times Higher Education’s World Academic Summit at the National University of Singapore, featured 86 countries, up from 81. Covenant University is ranked 601- 800, out of more than 1,250 higher education institutions on the list, same with the University of Ibadan. University of Nigeria, Nsukka, is ranked 1001+.4.

1. Challenges of Modern laboratories/Equipments

Many Nigerian universities lack modern laboratories to carry out research work. Every year thousands of young scholars from Nigeria travel out to carry out research work on their thesis or research work. Physics, Chemistry, Biology, and computer labs in most Nigerian universities lack the necessary equipment to carry out simple research work. Enogholase (2013) stated that students were using kerosene stoves instead of gas burners to conduct experiments, specimens were kept in bottles instead of the appropriate places where such specimen should have been kept.

Conflicts and Conflict Management in Nigerian University Educational System

Conflict is an inevitable friction in any organization and conflict in higher education institutions is inescapable. Conflict exists at every level of our academic world and while conflict can be negative and can cause deep rifts in the framework of the institution, it can also be used as a tool to take the institution and the people in it from stagnation to a new level of effectiveness, however what makes the difference is conflict management (Holton, 1998). Conflicts will always occur but a well managed conflict will not degenerate to violence. Every conflict in tertiary institutions and insecurity degenerated because their causes were not properly managed or that the conflicting parties did not explore the power of communication and conflict manager’s personality in resolving the crises (Agbonna; Yusuf & Onifade, 2009).

Concept of Conflict

Conflict is a dysfunctional, destructive, and the same time as a catalyst for change, creativity and production (Posigha & Oghuvwu, 2009). Conflict results from human interaction in the context of incompatible ends and where one’s ability to satisfy needs or ends depends on the choices, decisions and behaviour of others. It is the result of interaction among people, an unavoidable concomitant of choices and decisions and an expression of the basic fact of human interdependence (Adejuwon & Okewale, 2009). Wilmost and Hocket (1998) assert that conflict is an expressed struggle between at least two interdependent parties who perceived incompatible goals, scarce resource, and interference from other in achieving their goals. In other words, conflicts bring both danger and opportunity to both parties that involved, conflict can be destructive and constructive.

Conflict is a disagreement between two or more parties who perceive that they have incompatible concerns. Individuals, groups, departments, institutions, or organizations do experience conflicts whenever an action by one party is perceived as preventing or interfering with the goals, needs or actions of another (Bloisi 2007). Conflict can be described as a disagreement among groups or individuals characterized by antagonism and

hostility. This is usually caused by the opposition of one party to another, in an attempt to reach an objective different from that of the other party. The elements involved in the conflict have varied set of principles and values, thus allowing such a conflict to arise. (Conflict Research Consortium, University of Colorado, 2013).

Conflict has also been described as disagreement on the procedure of distributing power and resources in an organization. Basically, conflict is what occurs when two or more parties have divergent interests over distribution of resources and/or issues touching on their development. It is what can come up in the event of staff and student's interactions. It can emanate from school administrative cadre among students, or sometimes it can come up between school and its host community. It connotes a disagreement Over Social Issues, Beliefs and Ideologies (Horowitz And Borden 1995).

Conflict in the context of the University Educational System

The University community experiences countless conflict situations which impact on the education system with resultant effect on sustainable developmental goal. Without alternative methods, the conflict situations can contribute to a highly adversarial environment. Conflicts have made management of educational institutions in Nigeria to be the spotlight throughout the country. Educational institutions' conflicts in Nigeria are a phenomenon of great concern. Incidence and severity of institutional conflict has and continues to destroy the basic environmental conditions required to provide good environment for developing human resources for Nigeria. The chaotic situation has undermined many programmes aimed at enhancing the impartation of knowledge and skills in the future human resources for the country, aiming at achieving the sustainable developmental goal (Olugbile, 2005).

Education in Nigerian Universities' education is confronted with several conflicts. In the light of the sustainable development goal on education, this highlight these conflicts within the context of lack of a sound strategic plan, poor leadership, ineffective teaching and learning, poor researching activities, problems of inadequate infrastructure facilities, inadequate funding, poor international outlook (staff, students, research), the poor reputation of Nigerian Universities, academic corruption and fraud, low international ranking, lack of modern laboratories. Moreover, disputes over university reorganization, faculty performance, multimillion dollar grants, intellectual property, affirmative action, freedom of information, all are embodied into the conflicts within the Nigerian Universities educational system (Fatile and Adejuwon 2011).

Conflict Management Skill for Sustainable Development Goal in Nigerian University

Efficient and effective management of conflicts is fundamental to the development of any society, without exception to Nigerian universities. Conflict is managed in different ways, some focusing on interpersonal relationships and others on structural changes. Robinson; Roy & Clifford, (1974) advocates that managing conflict toward constructive action is the best approach in resolving conflict in organization. Proper management of conflicts would rather yield a positive force, rather than a negative one, which would threaten the individual or group.

Improper management of conflict leads to delays of work, disinterest and lack of action and in extreme cases, it might lead to complete breakdown of the group. Unmanaged conflict may result in withdrawal of

individuals and unwillingness on their part to participate in other groups or assist with various group action programmes in the institution. Parker (1974) asserts conflict to be an attendant feature of human interaction and cannot be eliminated; however, its proper management and transformation are essential for peace and progress in human society. Fatile and Adejuwon (2011) gave a highlight of conflict management skills are as follows:

1. Developing a Constructive Communication Process

In resolving university conflict, developing a constructive communication process and influential conflict negotiator's personality are very important. A great deal of numerous conflicts could be managed and guided from disrupting university efforts towards attaining its manifest and latent goals if the conflicting parties are systematic, logical and efficient in the way they communicate their grievances, situation of the conflict and their readiness to negotiate for peace and considering the personality of the negotiator mediating the resolution process (Agbonna; Yusuf& Onifade, 2009).

- Utilizing Appropriate Leadership Style

Conflict management in universities demands appropriate leadership style of the school administrator or chief executive. Demers in Magaula (2007) articulated three strategies of peaceful crisis resolution between and among warring parties; mediation, arbitration and reconciliation. Leaders should employ each of the approaches to resolve crisis among and between aggrieved parties in the university, avoiding propaganda and cognitive discrepancy in communication to discourage rumor, which distort third party's understanding of the conflict and may hamper its involvement in the resolution of the conflict (Bray, 1999).

- Timely and Sincere Communication

Communicators in University conflict management should be timely and sincere. (Agbonna & Okafor, 2008) encourages timely delivery and sincerity in communicating their messages of peace, assurance of restoring power and promise of cooperation toward resolution process. This gives a clear stance of the conflict management team and the progress made so far in resolving the conflict. Positive timely communication reveals the strength of the communicator to work for peace and for the interest of all, alleviate of victimization, and reduces tension in conflict situation.

- Develop a Democratic (Dialogue) Approach

University authorities should handle every university affair with a democratic approach; involve representative of all stakeholders for dialogue in decision-making process especially on issues that borders on the college. Maintaining a very cordial relationship between the university authorities and the college stakeholders by involving every representative in decision making process have been the most effective strategies of curbing conflict (Adeyemi, et al 2010). More importantly, in cases that involve university authority and the government of the country is recommended to dialogical in approach to reduce campus unrest (Aluede 2001).

- Develop Curriculum for Conflict management Courses

There is need for universities to employ educational approach by developing a curriculum for courses relating to conflict management and resolution, peace education, civic education, good governance, basic and human rights, separation of powers of government, the legislature, and the judiciary, bill of rights, social justice, respect and the rule of law, and virtues of peace, tolerance, patience and respect for life etc for all members of society. With all students being educated in conflict prevention, management and resolution, this will enable all Nigerian students will be grounded in the knowledge of handling non-violently all forms of conflict encountered with other Nigerians. This act will create the in the minds of upcoming generation the culture of peaceful coexistence and project Nigerian universities a location for the promotion of dialogue, understanding and tolerance (Magagula, 2007),

- Non-Violent Strategy Approach For Managing Conflicts

University management and the nation's leaders should create a non-violent strategic approach that will give room for discussion in managing conflicts the tertiary institutions in the country. Focus should be more on preventive strategies, appeal for peaceful persuasion, without compromising the school objectives and the exclusive right of the college; this is a display of rich experience and sound judgment of conflict situation. And it will definitely reduce crisis in schools rather than curative measures in conflict resolution (Agbonna, 2009).

Conclusion

Universities are still relevant in the process leading to achieving the sustainable developmental goal of education, in spite of the challenges and conflicts within the university education system. Sustainable development goal for education has been looked into in this article; Nigerian university system in the context of sustainable development is analyzed with the conflicts and challenges confronting them. The paper stressed the importance of developing a constructive communication process that will influence conflict negotiator's personality and utilizing appropriate leadership style of the school administrator for resolution process. Communication in University conflict management should be timely and sincere to alleviate victimization, and reduces tension in conflict situation. University authorities should approach every university affair democratically or dialogical by involving every stakeholder in decision making process. There is need for universities to employ educational approach by developing a curriculum for courses relating to conflict management and resolution, to create the in the minds of upcoming generation the culture of peaceful coexistence and project Nigerian universities a location for the promotion of dialogue, understanding and tolerance. Lastly, the University management and the nation's leaders should create a non-violent strategic approach that will give room for discussion in managing conflicts on tertiary institutions issue in the country.

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